

DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERISATION OF A NEW HIGH DAMPING COMPOSITE: Mg_2Si/Mg

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SUMMARY: A new, lightweight, high-damping material has been processed and characterised. It is a magnesium based composite with unidirectional Mg_2Si fibres. This natural composite has been produced by unidirectional solidification of a Mg-Si eutectic alloy (1.34 wt% Si) or near eutectic alloy (2 wt% Si). Mechanical strength was measured through tensile tests and the damping capacity was deduced from internal friction measurements in a low frequency torsion pendulum. The results show that these composites have a tensile strength comparable with industrial magnesium cast alloys such as AZ63 and a damping capacity which is 10 to 100 times higher. The mechanical properties and damping capacity are interpreted in terms of sample microstructure with emphasis on the effects of matrix and fibre orientation on the dislocation mobility.

KEYWORDS: damping capacity, mechanical strength, magnesium, unidirectional fibres, dislocations, microstructure

INTRODUCTION

Modern technology tends to suppress mechanical vibrations for social and economic reasons. Mechanical vibrations produce undesirable noise and can affect the precision of a machine-tool or cause fatigue-induced rupture of devices. These mechanical vibrations can be reduced in many ways, for instance by using external dampers or by increasing the inertial masses. However, these solutions are not always applicable, particularly in transport systems, which require lightweight and small structures [1]. Thus, contemporary transport systems need low-density materials which exhibit simultaneously a high-damping capacity and a high mechanical-strength. These properties are often incompatible [2] because the microscopic mechanisms which are involved in strengthening and in damping are not independent [3]. It is therefore important to develop new materials such as two-phase composites in which each phase can play a specific role: strengthening or damping.

Pure magnesium is known to exhibit a very high damping capacity [4], but its mechanical strength is low [5]. This metal can be hardened by introducing second phase precipitates which are able to pin dislocations, in order to avoid plastic deformation and thereby to increase the yield stress. However, if the mechanical properties are better in magnesium alloys than in pure magnesium, the damping capacity is lost in most of them [5]. A pure magnesium matrix reinforced with high-strength fibres is hence a good candidate for a high-damping composite. Actually the damping capacity of magnesium is due to dislocation vibration [6]. In order to obtain a high damping, this implies that the dislocation loops, which

are defined between the pinning centres, must be relatively free to vibrate. Thus, the magnesium matrix has to be relatively pure. In other words, in order to keep the damping capacity high, attention must be paid to the choice of the alloying elements, whose solubility in magnesium has to be low enough.

In this context, Mg - Si alloys have been studied as a system of low solubility because silicon is almost insoluble in magnesium (solubility lower than 30 ppm) [7]. Using the eutectic composition properties, a Mg-Si eutectic alloy (1.34 wt% Si) or near eutectic alloy (2 wt% Si) is converted into a magnesium matrix composite with Mg₂Si fibres by unidirectional solidification. The obtained natural composite is formed by a pure magnesium matrix reinforced with a low fraction of Mg₂Si fibres. So the dislocation loops can be long enough to vibrate and dissipate energy while pinning by fibres avoids plastic deformation.

This paper presents Mg₂Si / Mg composites which were processed by unidirectional solidification and characterised by optical and transmission electron microscopy, by tensile tests and by mechanical spectroscopy, i.e. measurements of the internal friction and of the elastic shear modulus as a function of temperature for different samples.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Mg₂Si / Mg composites were processed by unidirectional solidification of two different alloys. The grade A was an eutectic alloy (1.34 wt% Si) of low purity and the grade B was a near eutectic alloy (2 wt% Si) of medium purity, the mean impurity concentration is about 0.15%. Unidirectional solidification was performed using the same process as the Bridgman method for single crystal growth [8]. In a controlled atmosphere, a graphite crucible containing the alloy is moved in a vertical thermal gradient furnace. If the solidification surface is plane, the solid phase growth is regular and a two phase composite expands with vertical Mg₂Si fibres in a pure magnesium matrix. This solidification mode can occur if the alloy concentration is the eutectic concentration or near eutectic concentration. The solidification rate (v) and the distance between fibres (λ) are related by [9]:

$$\lambda^2 v = \text{const.} \quad (1)$$

Plate shape specimens were cut from the solidified rods by spark machining, in such a way that the sample axis is parallel to the solidification direction, i.e. parallel to the fibres.

The mechanical properties have been studied by classical tensile tests which provide the 0.2% yield stress, the tensile strength and the rupture strain.

Damping properties were deduced from mechanical spectroscopy measurements [10]. When a material vibrates under low stress excitation (much lower than the elastic yield stress) anelastic deformation is responsible for energy dissipation.

In a free-decay inverted torsion pendulum, the internal friction (IF) at low frequency ($\sim 2\text{Hz}$) and at a strain amplitude of about 10^{-5} is given by:

$$\text{IF} = \frac{1}{n\pi} \ln \frac{A_0}{A_n} \quad (2)$$

where A_0 and A_n are the amplitude of the first and the n^{th} oscillations. The shear modulus (G) was determined by the following equation [11]:

$$G = \frac{8\pi\ell If^2}{a^4} \quad (3)$$

where a is the sample thickness, ℓ its length, I the pendulum inertia momentum and f the vibration frequency.

A forced, inverted torsion pendulum, which allows one to vary the frequency in a wider range (10^{-3} to 10 Hz), was also used. In this case, the internal friction is given by:

$$IF = \tan(\delta) \quad (4)$$

where δ is the phase lag between the strain and the applied stress.

RESULTS

Sample Microstructure

Unidirectional samples were processed from both alloys. Fig. 1 displays two pictures obtained by optical microscopy on an unidirectional sample solidified at 0.5 mm/min. One can see that the Mg_2Si fibres are parallel to the direction of solidification.

Fig. 1: a) Lengthways image of an unidirectional sample. b) Transversal image of the same sample. Mg_2Si fibres are parallel to the solidification direction

Depending on the solidification rate (or crucible speed in the furnace), thermal gradient and alloy purity, the sample structures can be rather different. If all the conditions are properly balanced, i.e. a high thermal gradient, a low solidification rate and a high alloy purity [8, 9], the Mg_2Si fibres are parallel to the direction of the thermal gradient (Fig. 1). Moreover, the distance between fibres depends on the solidification rate as predicted by Eqn 1, with a different constant for each alloy (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Distance between fibres versus the solidification rate in a log-log graph. According with the error margins, the points follow the Eqn 1, with two different constants for both alloys, because of the different compositions

In addition, the matrix also exhibits a crystallographic orientation with the c-axis of the hexagonal structure parallel to the solidification direction. Fig. 3 is a Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) diffraction pattern associated with a magnesium grain, cut perpendicularly to the solidification direction. The hexagonal symmetry indicates that the matrix, which has an hexagonal structure, has its c-axis parallel to the specimen axis, i.e. the basal planes are perpendicular to the solidification direction.

Fig. 3: MET diffraction pattern for a magnesium grain. The c-axis of the hexagonal structure is parallel to the solidification direction (photo by Christian Verdon)

Without good conditions, randomly oriented short fibres are obtained, but the matrix nonetheless exhibits an oriented c-axis. A disoriented matrix can be obtained by natural solidification. Unidirectional specimens were obtained from grade B alloy for all tested rates, i.e. from 0.2 to 8 mm/min. Unidirectional specimens were obtained from the grade A alloy only for low solidification rates, between 0.2 and 0.7 mm/min.

Mechanical Properties

Tensile tests have been performed on these composites. Fig. 4 displays the mean ultimate tensile strength of different samples, in which the Mg₂Si fibres are parallel to the tensile

stress, as a function of the distance between fibres. One can see that the tensile strength is higher when the distance between fibres is lower, i.e. when the solidification rate is higher. For the shortest distances between fibres, the tensile strength is comparable with the industrial magnesium cast alloys such as AZ63 [5].

Fig. 4: Mean ultimate tensile strength of unidirectional samples versus distance between fibres. The tensile strength is higher when the distance between fibres is smaller. The dotted line corresponds to the level of the as cast AZ63 alloy

Internal Friction Spectrum

The Mg_2Si / Mg natural composites are characterised by a high damping capacity. Fig. 5 displays the internal friction (IF) and the elastic shear modulus (G) as functions of the temperature, measured in a specimen annealed during 4 hours at 600 K. Curves were measured by means of a low frequency torsional pendulum on a sample of grade A alloy solidified at 0.5 mm/min, but the damping general features are similar in all studied samples and with all measurement methods.

The internal friction is high and rather constant. It exhibits a broad maximum at about 200 K and a smaller one at about 400 K. The shear modulus exhibits an unusual behaviour: although modulus usually increases with decreasing temperature, this material presents a decreasing modulus with decreasing temperature between 430 and 350 K. Both the damping and the shear modulus exhibit large hysteresis during thermal cycling: damping is higher and modulus lower during heating than cooling. When the temperature is kept constant after heating, the damping decreases continuously and the modulus increases until they reach the values of isothermal equilibrium.

Fig. 5: Internal friction (IF) and shear modulus (G) versus temperature in a sample annealed 4 hours at 600K. IF is high and presents two maxima at 200 and 400K. G presents an unusual decrease between 430 and 350K. Both curves exhibit a large hysteresis

Effects of the Measurement Parameters on the Internal Friction

One way to understand the microscopic origin of the damping is to study the internal friction spectra, in particular the maxima of internal friction. Actually the microscopic phenomena, such as twinning or gliding of dislocations interacting with points defects, induce specific behaviour of the internal friction as functions of different parameters, as the strain amplitude or the frequency [10, 12]. The study of these dependencies generally allows one to determine some characteristic values of the phenomenon such as its activation energy and thus to deduce the involved phenomenon.

The study of the internal friction at different frequencies does not reveal a clear shift of the maxima, although a modification of the curve shape is observed. Fig. 6 displays the internal friction measured at room temperature (290K) as a function of the strain amplitude. The curve indicates a clear dependence on the amplitude. This reveals that the involved microscopic mechanism is complex.

Fig. 6: Internal friction versus strain amplitude at 290K. The internal friction depends on the strain amplitude

Moreover, the internal friction also depends on the heating or cooling rate. Fig. 7a displays the internal friction and the shear modulus versus the temperature at different heating rate (\dot{T}). One can observe that the internal friction is higher and the modulus lower when the heating rate is higher. Furthermore, Fig. 7b indicates that this dependence is complex. When $\dot{T} \neq 0$, the damping decreases linearly with \dot{T} , but the linear extrapolation for \dot{T} tending to zero (dotted line) is higher than the measured value for $\dot{T} = 0$. When heating is stopped, the stabilisation of the internal friction take a longer time than the stabilisation of the temperature. So it is possible to distinguish two effects: linear dependence with \dot{T} value (3) and time dependence at constant temperature (2). These two contributions are added to the intrinsic internal damping (1).

Fig. 7: (a) Internal friction (IF) and shear modulus (G) versus temperature at different heating rates: 0 K/min, 0.5 K/min, 1 K/min, 2K/min. The internal friction increases and the shear modulus decreases when the heating rate increases, (b) Internal friction (IF) versus heating rate (\dot{T}) at 220K. The internal friction is composed of three parts. (1) Intrinsic damping, (2) time dependant damping and (3) heating rate dependant damping

Effects of the microstructure on the internal friction

To enhance the composite properties, it is important to localise and to understand the mechanism of damping. Another way to obtain this information is to study the damping behaviour as a function of the sample structure.

Fig. 8 displays the internal friction versus the temperature measured with the forced torsion pendulum in different samples, in which the c-axis of the hexagonal structure of the Mg matrix is parallel to the sample axis. One can see that the Mg_2Si fibre phase morphology has no obvious influence on the damping capacity.

Fig. 9 presents the internal friction spectra of three specimens: one specimen (1) where the Mg matrix c-axis and the Mg_2Si fibres are parallel to the specimen axis, a second one (2) where only the Mg matrix c-axis is aligned along the specimen axis, the Mg_2Si fibres exhibiting no preferential orientation, and a third one (3) in which neither the Mg matrix nor the Mg_2Si fibres show any orientation. In the two first cases, where the Mg matrix c-axis is oriented, the internal friction level is high. On the contrary, the internal friction is lower by a factor two or three in the sample which does not exhibit any structural orientation. One can deduce that neither the distance between fibres nor the fibre orientation modify significantly

the internal friction level. On the contrary, the orientation of the matrix has a great influence on damping.

Fig. 8: Internal friction versus temperature in unidirectional samples of grade B alloy with different solidification rate: (1) 8 mm/min, (2) 5 mm/min, (3) 2 mm/min, (4) 1 mm/min, (5) 0.7 mm/min, (6) 0.5 mm/min, (7) 0.2 mm/min. The distance between fibres has no clear effect on the damping capacity

Fig. 9: Internal friction versus temperature in an unidirectional fibres/matrix sample (1), in an oriented c-axis matrix sample (2) and in a disoriented sample (3). Both the oriented c-axis matrix samples IF spectra have similar shape and height, but disoriented sample has much lower amplitude

DISCUSSION

Sample Structure

Both alloys can be unidirectionally solidified, with Mg_2Si fibre structures in agreement with Eqn 1, but the rates which are required to solidify unidirectional composites and the constant

which appear in Eqn 1 are different. This means that the involved solidification mechanism is the same in both cases and correspond with the well known theory of unidirectional solidification [8, 9], but the involved parameters are merely different.

The mechanism of unidirectional solidification is based on the fact that both phases solidify together at the same time. The distance between fibres depends on the solidification rate as shown in Eqn 1, because it corresponds to an equilibrium between the needed energy to initiate a new phase and the energy to grow the existing phases. The major difference between the two alloys is the impurity concentration. In fact, the grade A alloy contains more impurities. All impurities are sites which might seed new phases, so the constant appearing in Eqn 1 depends on the alloy purity. Moreover, these impurities disturb the regular growth of the fibres, and the unidirectionality can be obtained only if the solidification rate is slow enough. A pure enough alloy is hence necessary to obtain a small distance between fibres. As the grade B alloy is purer than the eutectic alloy, finer structures can be obtain with this alloy.

Mechanical Properties

The preliminary tensile tests are very promising. Although a large dispersion of the results, one can clearly see that the tensile strength is enhanced when the distance between fibres is small, i.e. when the solidification rate is high. These tests were performed on prismatic samples with a small cross section of 6 mm². Some edge effects are certainly responsible for the dispersion of the results, because the stress accumulation at corners facilitate the formation of cracks. Furthermore, the presence of oxides induces some porosity during the solidification, which decreases the mechanical strength.

Future work will be to optimise the processing of this composite and to find the best sample configuration for tensile tests. But already, for the lowest distances between fibres, the tensile strength is comparable with the industrial magnesium cast alloys such as AZ63.

Internal Friction Spectrum

Modulus Anomaly

Materials usually have a decreasing modulus as temperature increases. In these composites, on the contrary, the shear modulus increases between 350 and 430 K. This anomaly can be interpreted as follows: At the solidification temperature, the composite is at the equilibrium as it concerns the internal stresses, i.e. no internal stress appears between matrix and fibres. When the composite is subjected to an external stress such as torsion, the fibres are in extension. The high Young's modulus of the fibres acts as a restoring force, so the shear modulus of the composite is enhanced. During cooling, due to the thermal expansion coefficient mismatch, the internal stresses at the interface between fibres and matrix increase. These stresses can be first relaxed by dislocation creation and motion, but when the temperature decreases below a given temperature this relaxation is not sufficient, and the internal stresses compress the fibres. These compressed fibres are bent, they are no longer in extension under the external stresses and thus they can have no more effect on the shear modulus. So the shear modulus of the composite decreases to the modulus of the pure magnesium.

In other words, at high temperature the fibres participate in the modulus: the modulus is high and at low temperature the fibres do not participate in the modulus, hence, the modulus is low. This phenomenon occurs during each thermal cycle and explains the modulus anomaly.

Damping Behaviour

The samples exhibit a high damping, as was desired. But, the internal friction level depends strongly on the sample microstructure (Fig. 8). In order to manage the internal friction level, it is thus important to localise and understand the mechanisms which lead to the high damping. Fig. 6 and 7 indicates that the involved phenomenon is complex, nevertheless some possible interpretations can be explored.

Fig. 8 and 9 show that only the matrix orientation significantly influences the internal friction, but neither the fibre orientation nor the distance between fibres does. Hence, the observed effects may be due to a microscopic phenomenon which occurs in the matrix, such as motion of dislocations, twinning or defect movement. It is well known [2, 4, 6] that internal friction in pure magnesium is due to dislocation motion in the basal planes. Therefore, the composites have a rather good damping capacity if the applied stress is in a preferred orientation to induce dislocation vibration and if the dislocations are free enough to vibrate. This explains the fact that the damping capacity is higher when the c-axis of the matrix is perpendicular to the stress, i.e. when the c-axis is aligned along the sample axis, as shown in Fig. 9.

In other words, if the matrix is c-axis oriented and if the magnesium matrix is pure, the damping must be high. As the matrix c-axis orientation is guaranteed when the fibres are unidirectional, mechanical properties of this composite can be optimised without care to the damping capacity. As presented in the introduction, the high-damping capacity and the high-mechanical strength can be reached in these composites, because the involved mechanisms are independent.

However, a large dispersion in the internal friction occurs between each measured sample (Fig. 8). Previous works [4, 6] have shown that the dislocation motion in the basal plane is controlled by their interaction with points defects, more precisely, the interaction consist in pinning and depinning of the dislocations from the points defects. Thus internal friction spectra are very sensitive to the impurity concentration. Fig. 6 confirms this interpretation, but the shape modification with the frequency indicates that the interaction between dislocations and point defects is not a pure pinning-depinning mechanism. The dependence of the internal friction on the frequency permits one to suppose a dragging of point defects of higher mobility.

Transient Internal Damping

The internal friction depends on the heating or cooling rate (\dot{T}). Such a dependence, called transient internal damping, has already been observed in some composites [13]. This is due to the thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between the matrix and the fibres. But, the dependence on \dot{T} value is more complex than effects commonly reported in literature. Usual dependence is linear, but here there are two different effects depending on the \dot{T} value. Fig. 7 shows that when $\dot{T} \neq 0$ damping decreases linearly with \dot{T} , as studied in literature. The main characteristics of such an effect is a dependence with $\dot{T}/(\sigma_0\omega)$ where σ_0 is the applied stress amplitude and ω is the circular frequency.

However, Fig. 7 displays also that the internal friction measured in isothermal conditions (at $\dot{T}=0$) is lower than expected by extrapolation of the spectra measured for $\dot{T}\neq 0$. Moreover, when heating is stopped, the internal friction takes a longer time to stabilise than the temperature. Internal friction is then composed of three contributions: the intrinsic damping measured in isothermal conditions, a contribution which depends on the temperature stabilisation time and a contribution which depends on the heating or cooling rate \dot{T} .

CONCLUSION

A new composite material has been developed and characterised. It is a natural composite formed by unidirectional solidification of a Mg-Si eutectic alloy (1.34 wt% Si) of low purity (grade A) or near eutectic alloy (2 wt% Si) of medium purity (grade B). Both the fibres and the matrix c-axes can be aligned in the direction of solidification. The distance between fibres depends on the solidification rate and on the alloy purity. The grade B alloy give access to the finest fibre structure, because of its higher purity. The unidirectional fibres enhance the mechanical strength up to some industrial magnesium cast alloys such as AZ63. The matrix orientation provides a very high damping capacity over a wide range of temperatures, without influence of the distance between fibres. These natural composites exhibit mechanical properties comparable with the ones of classical magnesium alloys with a damping capacity 100 time higher.

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